

FEDERAL SERVICE
FOR INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

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[H01L 21/28 \(2006.01\)](#)

(12) ABSTRACT OF INVENTION

Legal status: act (recent status updates: 20.09.2023)

Duty: учтена за 3 год с 14.12.2024 по 13.12.2025. Установленный срок для уплаты пошлины за 4 год: с 14.12.2024 по 13.12.2025. При уплате пошлины за 4 год в дополнительный 6-месячный срок с 14.12.2025 по 13.06.2026 размер пошлины увеличивается на 50%.

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(54) METHOD FOR MANUFACTURING A POWER SEMICONDUCTOR DEVICE WITH PRESSURE CONTACTS

(57) Abstract:

FIELD: power semiconductor devices.

SUBSTANCE: invention relates to the manufacture of power semiconductor devices with clamping contacts and can be used, in particular, for the manufacture of semiconductor elements of devices used in switching devices for capacitive electric energy storage devices of electrophysical installations. A method for manufacturing power semiconductor devices with pressure contacts includes manufacturing a semiconductor element with a contact surface covered with a metal layer on the side of the silicon structure and connecting the semiconductor element with a conductive gasket by low-temperature sintering using a silver-containing paste, while determining the actual area of the contact surface before sintering, and the thickness of the silver-containing paste layer is set taking into account the actual area of the contact surface before sintering.

EFFECT: invention provides an increase in the actual area of the contact surface after sintering with an optimal consumption of silver-containing paste and an increase in the resistance of semiconductor devices to the effects of high-power current pulses.

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